

FUNCTIONAL-SEMANTIC ANALYSIS OF CONDOLENCES

Mavlanova Oybarchin Sheraliyevna

National University of Uzbekistan

Teacher

barchin95.komilova@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7238134>

Annotation: The present study is an attempt to make a linguistic presentation to the concept of condolences in English. This study aims at describing condolences from a functional-semantic and a pragmatic point of view. Moreover, this study is intended to show the grammatical structures of condolences.

Key words: semantics, condolences, pragmatics, grammatical structure, utterances, implicit condolences, explicit condolences, sympathy.

The main function of language is as communication medium. Language allows people to say things to each other and to express their communicative needs. In the interaction setting, people make use of language variation. This interaction causes them to use certain utterances, which are used for specific goals or purposes. A condolence utterance is one of these utterances. Condolences are one of the communicative speech acts. They are expressions, which are designed to convey one's sympathy on the occasion of someone's death. Losing someone close is a very painful experience. One can never really underestimate the power that words hold. In times of grief, especially, they provide utmost comfort. It is always comforting for the bereaved to hear kind words from his relatives or friends. So, condolences are very important.

The origin of the word "condolence" conveys a profound message. There are two Latin roots: *com*, meaning "together", and *dolere*, meaning "to grieve". Condolences are expressions that are "all one can use to tell of one's sympathy". They are formal expressions of regret or sorrow to people who experienced the death of someone. Condolences need not involve an act the hearer is responsible for.

They express the feeling of compassion toward the hearer's sadness. Condolences are not just expressions of sympathy; they are also acts of active, conscious support and encouragement in the face of adversity. They reduce the pain of those affected. Usually condolences of any form are greatly appreciated by the mourner and his or her family. Recipients of condolences usually are not looking for sparkling originality, just a sincere expression of emotion. However, not saying the suitable words of condolences, the bereaved might feel hurt or angry. This might even lead to weakening of relationships or loss of friendships.

With examples, Smith proposes the following categories of condolences: classical stock condolence phrases and these condolence phrases are neutral to be appropriate for almost everyone, regardless of religious beliefs:

My thoughts are with you.

Please accept my or our deepest sympathy

Condolence phrases considering someone's religious beliefs for people who believe in a concept of heaven and hell, one may express the idea that he or she believes that the diseased is in heaven or looking down from heaven, as in:

May God comfort you.

May his or her soul find peace

Condolence phrases as quotes Poetry can be a source of comfort and can express sympathy. Some people choose meaningful quotes from poems or books they like. They use famous quotes from poems dealing with death and mourning to assist themselves in expressing their condolences.

“To live in hearts we leave behind is not to die “.

“Like a bird singing in the rain, let grateful memories survive in times of sorrow”

“May the blessings of love be upon you, may its peace abide with you, may its essence illuminate your heart, now and forever more”

Condolence phrases containing the condition of the diseased. It is convenient to mention the condition of the diseased in a condolence phrase if someone is a close friend to the survivors. Condolence phrases to survivors of someone who died from a lingering illness, for example, might include a note of appreciation that the pain and difficulty are over.

“I was sorry to learn of your mother's death, but I am glad to hear that her suffering has come to an end”.

Semantically, condolences have a social meaning, which refers to the use of language to preserve social contact rather than to exchange information or ideas. The use of condolences preserves and regulates social relations and it might even lead to strengthening of them. Social meaning is communicated through the ritualistic use of language, which is found in condolences. Moreover, the essential function of the social meaning lies in the emotive purpose of the utterance. The condolence utterance possesses this kind of purpose. Such type of language use is alternatively described as social or phatic communication.

Phatic communication, which is expressed in the form of condolences, is elicited by the occurrences that call for the sharing of experiences or at least a show of empathy. Phatic communication emphasizes experiences of social fellowship and the participation in social linguistic rituals. In phatic

communication, condolences have little information value, but instead they have the essential function of “oiling the wheels of social discourse” on certain occasions.

Condolences belong to “communicative” speech acts, which are different from “conventional” speech acts for example; sentencing, bequeathing, and appointing which are not primarily acts of communication and have the function not of communication but of affecting institutional states of affairs. Communicative speech acts are acts performed with certain communicative intentions whose recognition by the hearer is necessary for the acts to be successful. They express a certain attitude, and the type of speech act being performed correspond to the type of attitude being expressed. For instance, condolences express regret, pain or sorrow.

The list of used literature:

1. Allan , K . “Linguistic Meaning”. Vol. I. New York: Routledge and Kegan.1986, p 112
2. Austin, J.L. “How to Do Things with Words”. London: Oxford University Press. 1962, p 89
3. Bach, K. and Harnish. “Linguistic Communication and Speech Acts”. Cambridge: The MIT Press. 1979, p 45